

Computational Studies of the Sulfamethazine as an Antibiotic

Kavitha B^a, Yogi Babu N^b and Ramesh B^{c#}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Dr. APJ Abdul Kalam Government Degree College, Patancheru, Telangana, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Government Degree & PG College, Jammikunta, Telangana, India

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Abstract

Computational quantum chemistry is widely used to evaluate thermodynamic properties and electronic structure of Antibiotics at ground state. In the present work, the computer aided active conformation, potential energies, molecular structures; vibration frequencies of coordinates of atoms, bond lengths, bond angles and calculation of excited state properties of Sulfamethazine are determined by using Argus Lab 4.0.1 software. The best possible conformations of Sulfamethazine are proposed with a minimum potential energy of -82989.0383 kcal/mol.

Keywords: Computational studies, ArgusLab, sulfamethazine, antibiotics, HOMO, LUMO

1. Introduction

Theoretical chemistry comprises a number of different research areas; quantum chemistry, computational chemistry, molecular modeling and interdisciplinary specializations such as structure biology, biochemistry, biotechnology, pharmaceutical industries and bioinformatics. Antibiotics have attracted much attention as they are used as the effective chemotherapeutic agents to treat bacterial infections. The quantum chemistry calculations are used to evaluate thermodynamic properties and electronic structure of Antibiotics at ground state.

Sulfonamides or sulfanilamides belong to an important class of synthetic antimicrobial drugs that are pharmacologically used as broad spectrum for the treatment of human and animal bacterial infection

Sulfonamides, also popularly known as sulfa drugs, are found to have antibacterial properties, were discovered way back in 1930s. The sulfonyl group plays an important role as a key constituent of number of biologically active molecules. Sulfonamides occupy a unique position in the drug industry and exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities (Scozzafava and Supuran, 2000; Wilkinson *et al.*, 2007; Güzel *et al.*, 2007; Kim *et al.*, 2008; Crocetti *et*

al., 2009; Ghorab *et al.*, 2009; Scozzafava *et al.*, 2003). The first clinically used sulfonamide was named prontosil (**I**) that showed protective action against streptococci in mice. Prontosil was found to be active in vivo, but ineffective in vitro, which led to the conclusion that prontosil itself is not the active drug. When metabolized in the body, prontosil produces sulfanilamide (**II**), which is the real active agent.

The present work describes synthesis and the computer aided conformational analysis that is based on geometry optimization (active conformation) of drug by ArgusvLab software. Argus Lab is the electronic structure program that is based on the quantum mechanics predicts the potential energies, molecular structures; geometry optimization of structure, vibration frequencies of coordinates of atoms, bond lengths, bond angles and reactions pathway (Peng *et al.*, 1995).

2. Materials and method

The structure of Sulfa drugs like Sulfamethazine was drawn and constructed by using window based program of Argus Lab and ACD Lab Chem Sketch software. Conformational analysis (geometry optimization) of sulfur drugs was carried out by using PM3 semi-empirical QM parameterization (Stewart, 1989) within the Hartree-Fock calculation method using Argus Lab 4.0.1 software. Geometry of the molecule was converged after the molecule is drawn and cleaned in ArgusLab and the program then computes the energy until the maximum cycles reached for the convergence (stopping point) of the molecule. Grid data was produced to generate surfaces which is a cubic grid of points around the molecule where various properties can be calculated such as electron densities, electrostatic potentials for any state i.e. ground state =0 to excited states 1, 2, 3 etc. and any of the orbital. Argus Lab subsequently uses these grid files to display surfaces for the relevant properties. Computational advancements have generated various tools which are widely used for molecular modeling including structure construction, minimization and representation (Martin, 1998; Cruciani *et al.*, 1998; Dunn III and Hopfinger, 1998; Dewar *et al.*, 1985). The Sulfamethazine (**III**) molecule is utilized to determine 3D structure of molecule. Several computer programs were used to infer the shape of molecule from geometry optimization calculations.

3. Results and discussion

The perspective view, active conformations, Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital, Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbital, electronic excited states, potential energy geometry convergence graph and electrostatic potential mapped electron density of Sulfamethazine are shown in **Figure 1** respectively. The geometry optimized atomic coordinates, bond angles, dihedral angles and bond lengths of Sulfamethazine are presented in **Tables 1a-d** respectively. The Highest Occupied Molecular Orbital (HOMO) (**Figure 2a**) is a nonbonding type that is in the plane of the molecule while the Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbitals (LUMO) (**Figure 2b**) is a π molecular orbital perpendicular to the plane of the molecule. The positive and negative charges are indicated by blue and red color respectively. The geometry convergence map of Sulfamethazine has clearly showed a decrease in potential energy with the progress of rotation. The minimum potential energy was calculated to be -82989.0383 kcal/mol.

Figure 1: Perspective View of the Sulfamethazine drug

Table -1a: Atomic Coordinates of Sulfamethazine drug

S. No	Atoms	X	Y	Z
1	C	-2.495054	1.608071	0.521212
2	C	-3.828472	1.540388	0.050047
3	C	-3.949746	0.181425	-0.317026
4	C	-3.098202	-0.729199	-0.199529
5	C	-1.791575	-0.706773	0.326503
6	C	-1.682006	0.661866	0.632515
7	N	-4.743355	2.555725	-0.099275
8	S	-0.746480	-2.010852	0.727059
9	N	0.682361	-1.893486	-0.381524
10	C	1.736578	-0.998194	-0.377705
11	N	2.993513	-1.499551	-0.661573
12	C	4.082596	-0.634177	-0.536991
13	C	3.948317	0.814847	-0.309453
14	C	2.540737	1.220235	-0.127573
15	N	1.468290	0.324734	-0.095773
16	C	2.361913	2.507439	0.010664
17	C	5.317867	-1.061391	-0.587695
18	O	-1.280017	-3.278018	0.335880
19	O	-0.182870	-1.838198	2.030456
20	H	-4.622072	3.333758	0.504072
21	H	-5.686745	2.281973	-0.245386
22	H	0.948200	-2.778228	-0.789039
23	H	2.294160	3.573577	0.120742
24	H	6.356082	-1.334546	-0.649202

Table -1b: Bond angles of Sulfamethazine

S. No	Atoms	Bond Angles	Alternate Bond angles
1	2 1 6 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
2	2 1 20 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
3	1 2 3 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
4	1 2 7 (C)-(C)-(N)	120.000000	307.964574
5	6 1 20 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
6	1 6 5 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
7	1 6 23 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
8	3 2 7 (C)-(C)-(N)	120.000000	307.964574
9	2 3 4 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
10	2 3 21 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
11	2 7 24 (C)-(N)-(H)	120.000000	124.657989
12	2 7 25 (C)-(N)-(H)	120.000000	124.657989

13	4 3 21 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
14	3 4 5 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
15	3 4 22 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
16	5 4 22 (C)-(C)-(H)	120.000000	114.188575
17	4 5 6 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
18	4 5 8 (C)-(C)-(S))	120.000000	200.910665
19	6 5 8 (C)-(C)-(S)	120.000000	200.910665
20	5 6 23 (C)-(C)-(H)	92.100000	114.188575
21	5 8 9 (C)-(S)-(N)	92.100000	286.724350
22	5 8 18 (C)-(S)-(O)	92.100000	303.587174
23	5 8 19 (C)-(S)-(O)	120.000000	303.587174
24	24 7 25 (H)-(N)-(H)	120.000000	70.257681
25	9 8 18 (N)-(S)-(O)	92.100000	425.732935
26	9 8 19 (N)-(S)-(O)	92.100000	425.732935
27	8 9 10 (S)-(N)-(C)	120.000000	218.427741
28	8 9 26 (S)-(N)-(H)	120.000000	103.565222
29	18 8 19 (O)-(S)-(O)	92.100000	471.223100
30	10 9 26 (C)-(N)-(H)	120.000000	124.657989
31	9 10 11 (N)-(C)-(N)	120.000000	420.206471
32	9 10 15 (N)-(C)-(N)	120.000000	420.206471
33	11 10 15 (N)-(C)-(N)	120.000000	414.072275
34	10 11 12 (C)-(N)-(C)	120.000000	233.893264
35	10 15 14 (C)-(N)-(C)	120.000000	233.893264
36	11 12 13 (N)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	303.537949
37	11 12 17 (N)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	285.448771
38	13 12 17 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	209.521192
39	12 13 14 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	222.595017
40	12 17 28 (C)-(C)-(H)	180.000000	58.101149
41	13 14 15 (C)-(C)-(N)	120.000000	303.537949
42	13 14 16 (C)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	209.521192
43	15 14 16 (N)-(C)-(C)	120.000000	285.448771
44	14 16 27 (C)-(C)-(H)	180.000000	58.101149

Table -1c: Dihedral Angles of Sulfamethazine

S. No	Atoms	Dihedral angle	Alternate Bond angles
1	(C3)-(C2)-(C1)-(C6)	6.737110 2	180.000000
2	(N7)-(C2)-(C1)-(C6)	6.737110 2	180.000000
3	(C2)-(C1)-(C6)-(C5)	6.737110 2	180.000000
4	(C2)-(C1)-(C6)-(H23)	6.737110 2	180.000000
5	(C3)-(C2)-(C1)-(H20)	6.737110 2	180.000000
6	(N7)-(C2)-(C1)-(H20)	6.737110 2	180.000000
7	(C1)-(C2)-(C3)-(C4)	6.737110 2	180.000000
8	(C1)-(C2)-(C3)-(H21)	6.737110 2	180.000000
9	(C1)-(C2)-(N7)-(H24)	6.737110 2	180.000000
10	(C1)-(C2)-(N7)-(H25)	6.737110 2	180.000000
11	(C5)-(C6)-(C1)-(H20)	6.737110 2	180.000000
12	(H23)-(C6)-(C1)-(H20)	6.737110 2	180.000000
13	(C1)-(C6)-(C5)-(C4)	6.737110 2	180.000000
14	(C1)-(C6)-(C5)-(S8)	6.737110 2	180.000000
15	(C4)-(C3)-(C2)-(N7)	6.737110 2	180.000000
16	(H21)-(C3)-(C2)-(N7)	6.737110 2	180.000000
17	(C3)-(C2)-(N7)-(H24)	6.737110 2	180.000000
18	(C3)-(C2)-(N7)-(H25)	6.737110 2	180.000000
19	(C2)-(C3)-(C4)-(C5)	6.737110 2	180.000000
20	(C2)-(C3)-(C4)-(H22)	6.737110 2	180.000000
21	(C5)-(C4)-(C3)-(H21)	6.737110 2	180.000000
22	(H22)-(C4)-(C3)-(H21)	6.737110 2	180.000000
23	(C3)-(C4)-(C5)-(S8)	6.737110 2	180.000000
24	(C4)-(C5)-(S8)-(N9)	1.317616 2	90.000000
25	(C4)-(C5)-(S8)-(O18)	1.317616 2	90.000000

26	(C4)-(C5)-(S8)-(O19)	1.317616 2	90.000000
27	(C6)-(C5)-(S8)-(N9)	1.317616 2	90.000000
28	(C6)-(C5)-(S8)-(O18)	1.317616 2	90.000000
29	(C6)-(C5)-(S8)-(O19)	1.317616 2	90.000000
30	(C5)-(S8)-(N9)-(C10)	1.317616 2	90.000000
31	(C5)-(S8)-(N9)-(H26)	1.317616 2	90.000000
32	(N9)-(C10)-(N11)-(C12)	13.474221 2	180.000000
33	(N9)-(C10)-(N15)-(C14)	13.474221 2	180.000000
34	(C12)-(N11)-(C10)-(N15)	13.474221 2	180.000000

Table 1d: Bond lengths of Sulfamethazine

Sl. No.	Atoms	Bond Lengths	Bond order
1	2C-7N	1.375733	1.50
2	20H-7N	0.993189	Single bond
3	1C-6C	1.252629	1.50
4	5C-6C	1.408192	1.50
5	3C-4C	1.252111	1.50
6	2C-3C	1.414599	1.50
7	5C-8S	1.722005	1.50
8	8S-10O	1.429651	Double bond
9	22H-9N	1.006707	Single bond
10	9N-10C	1.376263	1.50
11	10C-11N	1.382271	1.50
12	11N-10C	1.398258	1.50
13	12C-17C	1.307658	Single bond
14	12C-13C	1.474572	1.50
15	13C-14C	1.473555	1.50
16	14C-15C	1.396872	1.50
17	14C-16C	1.308060	Single bond
18	10C-15-N	1.37964	1.50

Figure 2a: Electrostatic potential (ESP) mapped Electron density on Sulfamethazine

Figure 2b: HOMO and LUMOs of Sulfamethazine

4. Conclusions

The present work describes the computer aided geometry optimization (active conformation) and calculation of excited state properties of Sulfa drug like Sulfamethazine, by Argus Lab 4.0.1 software (Thompson, 2004). This work indicates that the best conformations of Sulfamethazine, was found to be -82989.0383 kcal/mol, which is the minimum potential energy calculated by Argus Lab software. At this point, the sulfamethazine will be more active to interact with the receptors. Such types of interactions are significant for drug- receptor interactions.

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